

Barcelona Declaration Working Group Sustaining Infrastructures

Sessions on
Open Research Infrastructures
and Related Initiatives - Report

September / October 2025

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Introduction

The Working Group Sustaining Infrastructures of the Barcelona Declaration examines how open infrastructures for research information can be sustainably supported across the research ecosystem. As part of this work, the Working Group is exploring different governance approaches, sustainability models, and forms of community engagement that underpin existing infrastructures.

In September and October 2025, the Working Group organized two knowledge-sharing sessions with open infrastructures (Session 1) and initiatives operating at the ecosystem level (Session 2) to discuss sustainability models and how these can be strengthened through community engagement, coordination, transparency, and strategic investment.

The sessions aimed at knowledge sharing and identifying where the Barcelona Declaration community (and the Working Group in particular), can most effectively contribute in supporting signatories as they transition toward open research information.

Session on Open Research Infrastructures

Overview

This session, held on 30 September 2025, aimed to learn directly from open infrastructures operating in practice and to better understand how they sustain their services, communities, and technical operations over time.

The discussion also explored how different organisational models shape sustainability challenges and what lessons can be drawn for institutions seeking to transition toward open research information

The session focused on three open infrastructures, each introduced in turn and framed by the Barcelona Declaration team (Bárbara Rivera López and Bianca Kramer).

- [OpenAlex](#), presented by Kyle Demes as an open, comprehensive index of the world's scholarly outputs and related entities, designed for full openness, reuse, and integration into other systems.
- [OpenAIRE](#), introduced by Natalia Manola as a federated, non-profit European scholarly communication infrastructure that advances open science through a combination of services, national networks, and capacity-building across many countries.
- [OpenCitations](#), represented by Chiara Di Giambattista as an open citation infrastructure hosted at the University of Bologna, providing interoperable, machine-readable citation data as a shared resource for the scholarly community.

Open Infrastructure Presentations

Open Alex

Core message

OpenAlex is designed as a fully open, reusable graph of the world's research, with a sustainability model that is grounded in openness across its data, API, code, and governance.

Key points

- Scope and purpose: OpenAlex organises research information at global scale, covering hundreds of millions of works and tens of thousands of sources, institutions, funders and topics, bringing these entities together into a unified open index.
- Strong emphasis on openness of data: All OpenAlex data is freely available and released under a CC0 licence, with full dataset dumps and persistent snapshots to ensure long-term availability. Its codebase is openly developed and archived for long-term preservation, reinforcing transparency and reusability.
- Multiple access modalities: OpenAlex provides multiple ways to access its data: complete data dumps for large-scale users, an open API that most users rely on, and a web user interface aimed at more general or non-technical audiences.
- Adoption and reach: the infrastructure has achieved wide adoption, with tens of millions of users, hundreds of citations, and thousands of mentions, indicating that OpenAlex already functions as a widely used component of the scholarly infrastructure landscape.
- Governance and organisational structure: OpenAlex is operated by ImpactStory, a US 501(c)(3) non-profit with no owners or stockholders. A Board of Directors has a legal obligation to act in the organisation's mission interest, while a Community Advisory Board provides input on business issues in an advisory capacity.

Sustainability

- The sustainability model combines philanthropic and grant funding for building new infrastructure (tracked transparently via the OurResearch grants listing) and operations maintained through revenue for services, including increased API usage, priority support, custom development and additional benefits.
- OpenAlex explicitly considers contingency scenarios (such as funding gaps, governance shocks, acquisition risks, or organisational burnout), reflecting an approach where long-term openness requires planning for possible failure modes

Summary

OpenAlex is structured as a fully open, non-profit scholarly infrastructure: open data, open API, and open code at its core. It is governed by a mission-driven board and supported by a mix of grants and subscription revenue. Its sustainability logic relies less on commercial ownership and more on openness, community uptake, and deliberate governance and contingency planning.

OpenAIRE

Core message

OpenAIRE is a European non-profit infrastructure for Open Science, centred on the OpenAIRE Graph as an open knowledge base of the global research landscape. It approaches sustainability as a systemic challenge with a model that supports not only the single Graph but a broader ecosystem of services, networks, and national structures.

Key points

- OpenAIRE identity and scope: OpenAIRE is a European scholarly communication e-infrastructure, operating as a non-profit organisation established in 2018 and built on a federated model that combines human capital and advanced ICT services. It builds on a long-standing network of experts (National Open Access Desks) active since 2009 and today includes 55 members from 36 countries, with collaborations extending beyond Europe to regions such as Latin America, Canada, Japan, Korea, China.
- Mission and ecosystem: OpenAIRE positions itself as an ecosystem combining infrastructure, community, and policy, supporting the co-shaping and implementation of Open Science in Europe and beyond. Its work spans three pillars:
 - Network: connecting people and national expertise,
 - Services: implementing open scholarly communication infrastructure
 - Training: building capacities.
- Approach to open research information: OpenAIRE emphasises that its goal is not to create a single, monolithic service or impose a single model for open information infrastructures, as this would be limiting. Instead, its approach is embedded within its broader mandate around Open Science, where open research information is one important component within a wider ecosystem of services and policies.

- Cost structure and core technical components: A major cost driver is the OpenAIRE Graph, which requires large-scale aggregation, curation, deduplication, enrichment, provenance tracking, and AI-readiness. Infrastructure costs include maintaining and scaling pipelines for billions of records, ensuring GDPR-compliant storage, and increasing computational needs. Other cost factors include:
 - standards and continuous updates
 - community feedback and training
 - participation in EOSC
 - global partnerships.

Sustainability

- The sustainability model combines EU project funding with national co-financing mechanisms, including subscriptions and tailored service agreements that support the maintenance and operation of core services. Achieving long-term sustainability requires stable co-financing arrangements and sustained commitments at both national and European levels, alongside a more secure and coordinated baseline of support capable of matching the scale and continued growth of OpenAIRE's infrastructure and services.
- OpenAIRE explicitly frames sustainability not as maintaining a static system, but as enabling continuous service evolution in response to the changing nature of research and the objects represented in the Graph. This perspective signals that long-term openness depends on the ability to evolve rather than merely persist, allowing the infrastructure to actively co-shape the research and innovation ecosystem instead of only describing it.

Summary

As a European non-profit organization, OpenAIRE powers a federated digital infrastructure for Open Science, interconnecting global research information and providing a range of supporting services. OpenAIRE frames sustainability

OpenAIRE frames sustainability not as a single business-model issue, but as a systemic challenge that depends on national commitments, continuous service evolution, and capacity-building to support open science at scale.

OpenCitations

Core message

OpenCitations provides open, interoperable citation and bibliographic metadata as a shared scholarly infrastructure, sustained through a combination of institutional hosting (University of Bologna), community backing, and governance aligned with open science principles.

Key points

- Alignment with open research information: open citation data as fundamental for transparent, auditable research assessment and for evidence-based science policy. Since 2010, it has advocated for and produced open research information, supporting the Barcelona Declaration as part of its long-standing commitment to openness.
- Mission: Its mission is to harvest, openly publish, preserve, and provide accurate metadata on academic publications and their citations, in both human- and machine-readable formats, for unrestricted reuse and analysis.
- Services and data infrastructure: OpenCitations runs two core services:
 - OpenCitations Meta: stores and delivers bibliographic metadata and assigns OMIDs (OpenCitations Meta Identifier) to every entity;
 - OpenCitations Index: records citations as first-class data entities identified with OCIs (Open Citations Identifier).

The data is interoperable, linkable, highly reusable, and published under CC0.

- Governance: OpenCitations is hosted within the Research Centre for Open Scholarly Metadata (University of Bologna). As of September 2025, its governance bodies include: OpenCitations Council (members), an International Advisory Board providing strategic guidance, a Director and a Management Team.
- Principles:
 - Openness: all data is CC0, all software is open source, and all services are free and will remain free.
 - Community: the infrastructure works for and with the community, guided by collaborative partnerships, community funding, and community participation in development and governance.

Sustainability

- The sustainability model combines institutional hosting at the University of Bologna with time-limited grants, in-kind contributions, and financial support from members and donors. This community-based approach situates sustainability not only in funding streams but also in collaborative partnerships, community participation in governance, and ongoing contributions to data provision, curation, and correction.

- OpenCitations links long-term sustainability to reciprocal engagement with its community rather than to revenue-generating services or commercial ownership. Continued openness therefore depends on sustained institutional support, active community involvement, and governance aligned with open-science principles to ensure that citation data remains openly available over time.

Summary

OpenCitations positions open citation data as shared scholarly infrastructure and sustains it through institutional hosting, community membership and donations, and strong alignment with open-science governance principles. Its sustainability is deeply tied to reciprocal engagement with its community, rather than revenue-generating services or commercial ownership.

Discussion

The conversation highlighted several shared challenges across infrastructures, as well as differences in their operating models.

Institutional support and increased workload

- Bianca Kramer (Barcelona Declaration) picked up on an earlier point by Natalia Manola (OpenAIRE) that institutional support is useful but increases overhead.
- Kyle Demes (OpenAlex) noted that while support requests can be time-consuming, they often lead to improvements that benefit many institutions, not just the one raising the issue.
- Chiara Di Giambattista (OpenCitations) agreed that their experience is similar and that needs raised by individual members often generate improvements for the broader community.
- Natalia Manola (OpenAIRE) explained that, in their case, institutional work is more demanding because it involves guiding institutions through open science practices, repository / CRIS aggregation, standards, and policy alignment; not just API access. This makes the institutional workload considerably heavier.

Different infrastructure models imply different sustainability challenges

- Natalia Manola (OpenAIRE) emphasized that the organization functions as an ecosystem: infrastructure + community + policy; rather than as a single service. For OpenAIRE, institutions expect support across all these layers.

- Kyle Demes (OpenAlex) and Chiara Di Giambattista (OpenCitations) agreed that each infrastructure has a different model and relationship with institutions, so sustainability challenges also differ.

Community engagement as a core component of sustainability

- Chiara Di Giambattista (OpenCitations) highlighted that OpenCitations' sustainability depends not only on funding but also on active community involvement: contributing data, governance input, feedback, and advocacy.
- Bianca Kramer (Barcelona Declaration) noted that all three presentations showed that sustainability includes openness, governance, and community participation, not only financial resources.

Hidden costs of broad disciplinary coverage

- Chiara Di Giambattista (OpenCitations) clarified that OpenCitations uses several sources, and that it is global in scope; social sciences and monographs are included, though not always in large volumes.
- Natalia Manola (OpenAIRE) added that disciplines like SSH and books often require working with specialized hubs (e.g., OA books initiatives, Diamond OA journals), which adds hidden costs for open infrastructures.

Session materials

- Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1818700>
- Recordings: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gpyO3TErTMw>

Session on Related Initiatives

Overview

This session, held on 14 October 2025, complemented the session focused on open infrastructures by inviting initiatives operating at the ecosystem level that aim to strengthen sustainability through funding coordination, transparency, and strategic investment.

The goal was to better understand how these initiatives define and support long-term sustainability of open infrastructures, whether different types of infrastructures require distinct approaches, and how the broader ecosystem of funders, institutions, and initiatives interacts.

The session brought together three related initiatives that play distinct but complementary roles in the global open infrastructure ecosystem. Each introduced in turn and framed by the Barcelona Declaration team (Bárbara Rivera López and Bianca Kramer).

- [Invest in Open Infrastructure \(IoI\)](#), presented by Katherine Skinner and Sarah Lippincott as an initiative that strengthens the global ecosystem of open scholarly infrastructure through evidence-based tools, strategic support, and innovative funding mechanisms that help institutions adopt, sustain, and invest in open systems.
- [SCOSS \(Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services\)](#), introduced by Rosalie Lack as a global initiative, identifies and endorses essential, non-commercial open infrastructures and helps them secure ongoing, diversified funding through relationships with library consortia, institutions, and funders.
- [TSOSI \(Transparency to Sustain Open Science Infrastructure\)](#), outlined by Maxence Larrieu as a new initiative focused on making financial support for open scholarly infrastructures visible, comparable, and normalised across institutions.

Related Initiatives Presentations

Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI)

Core message

IOI works to increase adoption of and investment in open scholarly infrastructure, combining landscape research, strategic support, and direct funding to build a coordinated, resilient ecosystem rather than a fragmented set of tools and services.

Key points

- Scope and purpose: IOI's overarching goal is to remove two key barriers to a thriving open research ecosystem: a lack of predictable long-term funding and the limited scale at which many infrastructures currently operate. It does this by:
 - Mapping and analysing the open infrastructure landscape (funding, governance, adoption).
 - Providing strategic support to individual infrastructures and networks.
 - Directly channeling funding to open infrastructures and the networks that implement and use them.
- Definition and framing of open infrastructure: IOI uses a pragmatic definition of open as the willingness and readiness to be discovered, accessed, identified, integrated, and reused.

Infrastructure is understood as the systems, tools, protocols, platforms, and networks that research communities rely on across the research lifecycle. IOI focuses on digital infrastructures that enable open knowledge to function at scale within the scholarly communication ecosystem.

- Core programmes and activities: IOI's work is structured around three main pillars:
 - Data Room (research & analysis): landscape research and data collections on how open infrastructures are funded, governed, and adopted, to identify high-leverage areas for collaboration and investment.
 - Strategic support (consulting): tailored support for infrastructures and networks on governance, financial models, and business strategy, translating field-level evidence into concrete sustainability plans (including work with arXiv and through the Catalyst project).
 - Funding programmes: a growing funding pillar that provides resources and strategic support to users and builders of open infrastructure, with a particular focus on Latin America and Africa. Its flagship is the IOI Fund for Network Adoption, offering multi-year, flexible funding plus IOI's guidance to help networks implement and scale open infrastructure.
- Stakeholders and governance: IOI brings together experience from open infrastructures, libraries, publishing, open science advocacy, digital preservation, and community-driven technology projects. The founding cohort and current team include

leaders from organisations such as Dryad, eLife, Wikimedia, Mozilla, Library Publishing Coalition, arXiv, New York Times, GitHub and university libraries worldwide.

- Tools and signals for sustainability: IOI provides several resources that help institutions and communities understand and strengthen the sustainability of open infrastructure:
 - Infra Finder: an online tool designed to support the discovery, comparison, and adoption of open infrastructures. It includes up-to-date, verified information provided directly by infrastructure providers and allows users to compare infrastructures side by side across more than 30 categories.
 - State of Open Infrastructure Report: IOI's annual landscape analysis that examines characteristics of open infrastructures such as governance, funding, adoption, and policy development.
It also identifies trends and future opportunities, offering strategic insights for stakeholders navigating changes in the research ecosystem.
 - ORBIT: Open Resilience: A report outlining five high-potential avenues for collective investment in open infrastructure: hosting, building, sponsoring, training, and cultivating.
It provides a structured way to think about how libraries and other institutions can support open infrastructure at scale.

Sustainability

- IOI receives support from philanthropic organisations and foundations, such as Arcadia, Wellcome, the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, and Schmidt Futures.
- The IOI Fund, which provides resources for implementing and scaling open infrastructures, functions as a flexible funding mechanism that supports networks in adapting, growing, and sustaining their use of open infrastructure.

Summary

IOI's sustainability work centres on strategic support for infrastructures to strengthen governance and financial models, through evidence, comparison mechanisms, and targeted investment pathways (including through the IOI Fund), designed to resource networks and institutions implementing and scaling open infrastructure.

These elements position IOI as both an ecosystem analyst and a funding actor, supporting greater coordination, resilience, and long-term viability across the open infrastructure landscape.

SCOSS: Global Sustainability Coalition for Open Science Services

Core message

SCOSS's core mission is to ensure the long-term sustainability of vital, non-commercial open science infrastructures by coordinating collective, diversified funding across libraries, consortia, and research organizations. SCOSS works to normalize institutional support for open infrastructure, positioning it as an essential service underpinning the entire research lifecycle.

Key points

- Identity and scope: SCOSS (formally established in 2017) is a global coalition composed of library consortia, research networks, national agencies, and international associations including SPARC Europe, LIBER, Latindex, and the Association of African Universities, the French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, Qatar National Library, INFLIBNET, and others.
Together, these organizations represent a worldwide network of stakeholders committed to sustaining non-commercial open infrastructures.
- Mission and role in the ecosystem: SCOSS seeks to ensure the sustainability of essential infrastructure that enables Open Science in practice. It does so by offering a coordinated cost-sharing framework through which the wider research community can collectively support the non-commercial services it relies on.
- What SCOSS does:
 - Endorses infrastructures for investment, identifying services essential to the open science ecosystem.
 - Facilitates multiple pathways for support, enabling libraries, consortia, and funders to contribute according to their capacities.
 - Mobilizes collective funding through coordinated appeals.
 - Promotes ongoing partnerships, encouraging institutions to embed support in regular budgets beyond the initial three-year campaign period.

Through this model, the funding framework connects consortia, individual institutions, and research funders to endorsed infrastructures.

- Coverage and infrastructure types: SCOSS has endorsed 19 infrastructures spanning the research lifecycle, including:
 - Publishing/Repositories: journals, books, preprints, datasets, software
 - Metadata infrastructures supporting discovery and research assessment
 - Identifiers, open monographs, open publishing, repositories, assessment tools, standards and strategy organisations

Geographical coverage includes North and South America, Africa, Europe, and additional global regions.

- Different communication challenges across infrastructures: SCOSS notes that infrastructures vary in how easily stakeholders understand and value them:
 - Services resembling collections or knowledge bases are more familiar and easier to explain. Examples include: arXiv, DOAB, DOAJ
 - Technical or abstract infrastructures (Software Heritage, RDA) often require more effort to communicate their critical role, even when indispensable to the ecosystem.
 - Even established infrastructures face challenges because there is no consistent culture of funding ongoing support for open infrastructures.

To address this, SCOSS is exploring ways to promote infrastructures by thematic areas aligned with institutional priorities, while emphasizing the interconnected nature of the open infrastructure ecosystem supporting the research lifecycle.

Sustainability

- SCOSS defines long-term sustainability as the ability to provide infrastructures with reliable and diversified funding streams, complemented by strong governance structures and active global community engagement including meaningful participation from board members. This places sustainability beyond purely financial considerations.
- It also includes safeguarding long-term access to knowledge by maintaining metadata standards and preservation practices, and ensuring that non-commercial open infrastructures remain openly available over time through the use of open standards.
- SCOSS supports long-term sustainability by the funding of open infrastructure: moving away from one-off or short-term contributions and embedding support directly into institutional budgets as “business as usual.” This is tied to building a culture in which open infrastructures are broadly understood as essential services.
- To make this shift possible, SCOSS uses collective funding appeals that encourage libraries, consortia, and research organizations to integrate sustained support into their regular financial planning, while also fostering partnerships that continue beyond the initial three-year funding cycle.

Summary

SCOSS positions sustainability as a collective responsibility across global library networks, consortia, funders, and institutions. Its model focuses on coordinated funding, diversification, governance, community engagement, and embedding open infrastructure support into routine institutional budgets. Through endorsements, thematic framing, and global coalition-building, SCOSS aims to normalize long-term financial and governance support for critical non-commercial infrastructures that underpin Open Science.

TSOSI. Transparency to sustain open science infrastructure

Core message

TSOSI is a shared, open data infrastructure that makes financial support for open science infrastructures visible and comparable, so that funding them stops being an ad-hoc extra and becomes a normal, institutional and policy-level commitment.

Key points

- Identity and scope: French-led, lightweight initiative that makes institutional financial support to open science infrastructures visible and comparable. It collects and curates data on who funds which infrastructures, at what levels, and through which channels. Although rooted in the French open science policy context, its scope is global, covering contributions from over a thousand institutions worldwide.
- Core programme and activities: TSOSI's core work focuses on collecting, enriching, and visualising financial support data for open science infrastructures. It gathers support information directly from infrastructures, harmonises it using identifiers (mainly ROR and Wikidata), and produces clear data visualisations that make funding patterns understandable and actionable. Its activities also include:
 - expanding the number of participating infrastructures
 - developing tools to detect duplicate or overlapping supports
 - integrating institutional-level data
 - incorporating user feedback to guide future development.

Together, these activities aim to make the funding landscape more transparent and to normalise sustained institutional support for open infrastructures.

- Definition and framing of open infrastructure:
 - TSOSI describes open infrastructure as non-commercial, community-driven services that underpin Open Science, such as DOAJ, DOAB, OPERAS, SciPost, and PeerCommunityIn. These infrastructures are characterized by openness in

their mission, governance, and outputs, and rely on institutional financial support rather than proprietary business models.

- At this initial stage, TSOSI takes a pragmatic approach to defining open infrastructure, working with operational definitions that can inform funding and policy decisions in practice, and refining them as the work evolves. Implicit in this framing is the understanding of open infrastructures as core public goods whose long-term sustainability depends on transparency regarding who funds them and at what level.
- Stakeholders and Governance: TSOSI is governed through a multi-layered structure involving policy bodies, infrastructure organisations, and user communities.
 - A Supervision Group (Ouvrir la Science!, French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, Université Grenoble Alpes, GRICAD) provides strategic oversight.
 - An Advisory Group (SCOSS, DOAJ, DOAB, OPERAS) offers domain expertise and alignment with the broader open infrastructure ecosystem.
 - A User Group (including Couperin.org, PeerCommunityIn, and SciPost) ensures that institutional perspectives shape development.

TSOSI operates in a project phase with roughly 1.5 FTE and is working toward a post-2026 sustainability model.

Sustainability

- TSOSI approaches sustainability by addressing a core problem in the open science ecosystem: the invisibility and fragmentation of financial support for open infrastructures. When contributions are not visible, they are treated as optional extras rather than essential, long-term commitments.
- By collecting, cleaning, and presenting funding data in a transparent way, TSOSI helps institutions recognise their own role in sustaining open infrastructures and encourages them to integrate support into regular, predictable budgets.
- Sustainability is not only about money, but about creating a culture where institutional support is normalised, trackable, and accountable, ensuring that non-commercial open infrastructures can remain openly available over time.

Summary

TSOSI shows that it is possible to map who funds which open infrastructures at national level, and that the result is a fragmented, largely invisible patchwork of short-term and irregular support for services that are actually critical to the research system.

Transparency is a precondition for sustainability: by making funding flows visible and comparable, TSOSI creates the basis for better coordination, helping institutions see who

pays for what, where gaps and free-riding occur, and where more predictable, structural and shared funding models are needed over time.

Discussion

The discussion across the three related initiatives (SCOSS, TSOSI and IOI) highlighted shared structural challenges in sustaining open infrastructures, as well as important differences in their approaches, incentives, and operating models.

Visibility and transparency as prerequisites for sustainability

A recurring theme across the session was that transparency is a prerequisite for both institutional decision-making and long-term accountability: without a clear view of who is supporting what, it is impossible to plan sustainably.

- Rosalie Lack (SCOSS) emphasised that the lack of visibility around institutional support (who funds what, at which levels, and through which channels) is one of the main structural barriers to sustainability. Without comparable information, institutions cannot reason about their own contributions or coordinate support strategies.
- Maxence Larrieu (TSOSI) reinforced this point through the TSOSI mapping results, showing how collecting and harmonising financial support data exposes patterns that are normally hidden gaps, duplication, and uneven responsibility across institutions.

The cultural shift: support must become the norm

The presenters emphasised that sustainable funding is not only a financial challenge but a cultural one.

- Rosalie Lack (SCOSS) highlighted that many institutions still treat contributions to open infrastructures as optional or “extra” expenditures, often embedded in ad hoc decisions or leftover budgets.
- Maxence Larrieu (TSOSI) showed how making institutional supports visible can accelerate a cultural shift: once mapped, institutions begin to recognise open infrastructure as an essential service rather than a discretionary expense.
- Katherine Skinner (IOI) echoed this perspective, emphasising that sustainability depends on coordinated, values-aligned investment rather than one-off payments or reactive funding cycles.

Different models, different sustainability challenges

The discussion highlighted that these three initiatives operate at distinct levels of the open infrastructure ecosystem, which means their sustainability challenges are also different but ultimately complementary.

- SCOSS mobilises collective support through coordinated fundraising campaigns but depends on institutions embedding those contributions into long-term, structural budgets.
- TSOSI does not raise funds; instead, it provides the evidence layer needed for strategic decision-making. TSOSI helps institutions understand where their support is most needed.
- IOI operates as both a research and funding organisation, combining landscape analysis, strategic consultancy, and a growing funding mechanism (the IOI Fund) that enables multi-year, values-aligned investment.

Together, these models illustrate a complementary ecosystem: TSOSI makes support visible and intelligible, SCOSS mobilises coordinated contributions, and IOI enables strategic, investment aligned with community needs.

Coordination and shared responsibility

The presenters converged on the idea that sustainability requires coordination across institutions, funders, and infrastructures.

- SCOSS noted that without coordination, some infrastructures become over-supported while others essential to the ecosystem remain fragile.
- TSOSI's mapping revealed similar patterns: significant disparities in who contributes, inconsistent levels of support, and free-riding behaviours that are otherwise invisible.
- IOI framed this challenge in terms of "alignment": ensuring that investment and adoption evolve coherently so infrastructures can scale sustainably over time.

Shared terminology and structured categories

There is a difficulty of comparing support models due to inconsistent terminology.

- SCOSS underlined the need for standardised language around support types and funding streams.
- TSOSI's categorical framework (mapping supported by type, channel, and consistency), was highlighted as a step toward creating a shared vocabulary for institutions, infrastructures, and funders.

Such harmonisation reduces friction and helps institutions incorporate structured support into regular planning.

Session materials

- Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18188253>
- Recordings: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nf_5px0Pjzs

What the Barcelona Declaration and the Working Group Sustaining Infrastructures could do

Taken together, the discussions across both sessions highlighted several areas where the Working Group Sustaining Infrastructures and the broader Barcelona Declaration community could add value in supporting the sustainability of open research infrastructures.

Strengthen shared messaging around open infrastructures

The sessions made clear that institutions often lack a coherent narrative for explaining why open infrastructures matter and why sustained investment is needed.

The Working Group could contribute by helping to clarify:

- The value, costs and risks associated with open infrastructures, including the fact that “open is cheaper, but not cheap.”
- How open infrastructures deliver public value, sovereignty, and resilience, particularly in contrast to dependency on proprietary systems.
- The hidden costs of sustaining infrastructures, including standards development, metadata curation, governance processes, integrations, user support, compliance, security, and long-term preservation.

A shared messaging framework could help institutions justify long-term investments and compare open infrastructures more fairly with commercial alternatives.

Bridge strategic ambition and operational implementation

Across both sessions, participants highlighted the persistent gap between high-level commitments and day-to-day institutional practice.

The Working Group could help bridge this gap by:

- Formulating key questions institutions should ask when selecting, funding, or evaluating infrastructures
- Clarifying what meaningful support looks like from different actors (e.g. baseline institutional funding, multi-year national commitments, community-backed contributions, policy mandates)
- Highlighting governance and funding arrangements that have worked in practice, without prescribing a single model.

Support shared learning through concrete examples

Several participants emphasised the need for honest documentation of real experiences, including challenges and course corrections.

The Working Group could therefore curate a repository of structured case studies documenting infrastructures and institutional journeys, including:

- The role of the infrastructure in the ecosystem
- Governance models and funding arrangements
- Services offered and community engagement
- Key challenges encountered, including approaches that did not work.

This type of resource could help institutions move from abstract commitments to practical support.

Develop practical tools for institutions and infrastructures

As a practical contribution, the Working Group could explore developing lightweight tools that help institutions and infrastructures structure their decision-making.

Possible approaches include:

- A Starting Point Framework outlining key considerations when (re)designing infrastructure or entering service agreements
- Decision checkpoints related to:
 - Value alignment and public mission
 - Governance structure and stakeholder voice
 - Workflow integration with existing systems
 - Data openness, portability and contingency planning
 - Long-term funding and risk-sharing arrangements

These checkpoints could draw on existing community frameworks such as the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure \(POSI\)](#), particularly its updated version 2.0.

Strengthen coordination across the ecosystem

Finally, the sessions highlighted the importance of coordination across infrastructures, funders, and initiatives.

The Working Group could contribute by:

- Facilitating a mutual learning network among institutions and infrastructures facing similar challenges
- Improving the legibility of the open infrastructure ecosystem, helping institutions understand how different services complement rather than compete with each other
- Exploring collaboration with initiatives such as SCOSS, IOI, and TSOSI to align advocacy, transparency efforts, and funding coordination.

Current activities of the Working Group Sustaining Infrastructures

Building on the discussions in the knowledge-sharing sessions, participants of the Working Group are now developing a set of activities to help institutions better understand and support the sustainability of open research information infrastructures.

This work include:

- Publishing a report and analysis synthesizing insights from the knowledge-sharing meetings
- Creating a case repository documenting sustainability approaches across infrastructures and institutions, providing practical and non-prescriptive guidance for institutional support
- Developing structured profiles of infrastructures and institutional implementation journeys
- Identifying key questions and decision points to support institutional implementation
- Compiling a shared knowledge base to support learning across institutions

Together, these activities aim to support signatories in moving from discussion to implementation by providing concrete examples, shared knowledge, and practical guidance for sustaining open research information infrastructures over time.